

STRATEGIES FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF INVASIVE PLANT SPECIES

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1 INTRODUCTION

The LEAP project directly addresses the challenges of the EU strategy for plastic packaging waste, in terms of replacing it with more sustainable materials; addresses the challenge of the transitioning to more sustainable resource management with a low ecological footprint. The idea of the LEAP project is to develop the next generation of advanced functional packaging that incorporates the biomass of non-native invasive plants and enables the production of new high- performance packaging solutions.

The project indirectly faces another challenge regarding the widespread and the lack of control methods for invasive alien plants. For thousands of years, humans have been transmitting plant and animal species, as well as other organisms, between different environments, either intentionally (importing cultivated, ornamental plants) or unintentionally (stitched passengers - ballast water, together with seeds, plants, fruits, various cargo). The species that were not originally presented in the environment are called a non-native species. The transfer of species between different environments have been on an even greater scale in the last few decades due to increased international trade (Strgulc Krajšek, 2016).

Only a small amount of the non-native organisms are able to survive in the new environment. Some species are unable to adapt to the new environment and their survival and reproduction depends on the help of humans. But there is still a small share of species that have a significant impact on nature and people. Usually, such species have strong adaptability, fast reproduction, spreading capabilities, undemanding in terms of environment and conditions, mechanisms for surviving unfavorable conditions, that contribute to their success in their new area. They are called invasive alien species (in the following IAS). IAS usually cause serious negative consequences in places outside their natural environment

(economic damage, health problems), especially have big negative impact on native biodiversity, ecosystem services (habitat degradation). In the new environment, they compete with native species for habitat, food, water, light and other important resources. IAS are also often carriers of different diseases and parasites against which native species are not resistant (Strgulc Krajšek, 2016).

IAS spread very quickly and form dense stands that can completely change ecosystems in the environment. Eradication of invasive plants is often very expensive and difficult. With effective strategies and measures we can restrict and limit their spread (Eler, 2018):

- a) primarily by preventing entry into the country (restriction of trade in potentially invasive organisms, customs inspections, quarantine),
- b) with early detection and timely removal (before flowering, suppression of smaller, initial populations),
- c) preventing and limiting the spread (washing of work machines, appropriate handling of excavated soil, greening the open areas),
- d) to regular control of already widespread species (mechanical, chemical, biological; removal of entire plants with root system, regular mowing).

The framework regulation that primarily covers non-native species in Slovenia is the Nature Conservation Act.

2 STRATEGY FOR ESTABLISHING A METHOD TO COLLECT AND CONTROL INVASIVE ALIEN PLANT SPECIES

Company Surovina, together with other project partners, is trying to develop and demonstrate a solution for the design of protective packaging made of lignocellulosic plant fibers, which will be an alternative to EPS packaging, also for heavier industrial products. Invasive plants will be used as a source of recyclable materials to produce paper pulp, and later protective packaging for household appliances. The key role of the company Surovina is to determine clear rules and develop the correct procedure for the removal, collection and pre-treatment of plant waste of invasive species for the establishment and demonstration of a circular-sustainable business model for the collection of lignocellulosic biomass, design and production of industrial packaging. The main purpose is the establishment of the new collection system of non-native plants and suitable preliminary preparation for the use of the packaging production. As a result, Surovina established a waste collection center at business unit in Maribor, where

they accept from individuals and companies invasive plants wastes of two different species: Canadian/Giant goldenrod and Japanese/Czech knotweed.

Figure 1. Invasive plants waste collection point at PE Pobrežje, Zrkovska 105, 2000 Maribor.

In the production of paper pulp, which is the first step in the manufacture of the more sustainable protective packaging, only lignocellulose can be use, which is mostly found in the stems. For the needs of using plants as an input material in new advanced processes, we need to remove the leaves, flowers and roots from the stems. For a compact and suitable paper pulp that can be used in the production of protective packaging, the stems must be properly dried and previously ground into smaller pieces. Since these are non-standard processes, most of the work is done manually, using various tools adapted to our needs.

Figure 2. Pre-treatment scheme of the invasive plants used in the manufacturing processes of protective packaging.

Removing and preventing the spread of IAS is essential, first and foremost to reduce the damage they cause to the environment and at the same time it is

necessary to consider the European Regulation No. 1143/2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species.

The suppression over IAS is the responsibility of the landowner. On private lands, the owners are known, while the maintenance of the public areas are carried out by the economic public services. In Slovenia, landowners are obliged to suppression of invasive plants from the genus *Ambrosia*, which is regulated by the Decree on measures for the control of harmful plants from the genus *Ambrosia*. For all other non-native species, prevention and control is recommended. To optimize the collection of non-native plant species, company Surovina prepared a questionnaire, based on which a strategy for the development of new collection system and the method of the pre-treatment of the invasive plant species were prepared. The invitation to complete the survey was send to all registered public service providers and municipalities.

Provider of public services carry out cleaning and maintenance of public areas, which also includes mowing and pruning of trees. Maintaining of green areas, also reduces and prevents the spread of non-native plants.

72 % of the public service providers have established the system for collecting and removing of non-native plant species. When removing invasive plants, it is crucial to take proper precautions and understand their life cycle. Improper disposal can allow invasive plants to regrow or be transported to previously uncontaminated areas. 44 % of the maintainers of public areas collect and remove IAS regularly, more than three times a year. About third remove IAS once a year, and 22 % only remove IAS on request. Cautiously handling of invasive plant parts is extremely important. Not every disposal method is appropriate for every species. Around third of the maintainers of public areas provide for the collected non-native plants the incineration, either handover them to the incineration facility or burn the debris on the site. 26 % handover the collected plants to composting facilities. Only a third of non-native species are handover to landfill sites, which is not a suitable disposal method for certain species, as they can regrow and spread (Data from survey: Removal, collection and management of invasive native plant species (and other green waste) by public service providers, 2023). Also, additional caution is required in aerobic and anaerobic decomposition processes, as the seeds of some plants are extremely resistant to the conditions and if the requirement parameters of hygienization are not met, incomplete destruction of the seeds may occur.

Slightly more than half of the public service providers remove and collect non-native plant species separately from native species, even in areas where plants

coexist (Data from survey: Removal, collection and management of invasive native plant species (and other green waste) by public service providers, 2023).

Proper disposal of removed invasive plant material is critical to the control process. Invasive alien plant species usually spread quickly and successfully in nature, their debris can re-root in an area or spread to another environment. To reduce their populations in the environment, it's important to remove the whole plant, even as much of the root system as possible; even a small portion can restart the infestation. Of course, this is possible in the case of individual specimens or smaller populations. In the case of larger populations, the regular mowing is necessary to reduce the populations. To be effective, you will need to mow or cut infested areas three or four times a year for up to five or more years. Almost half of the maintainers of public areas are aware of the proper control over the IAS, as they remove the entire plants (Data from survey: Removal, collection and management of invasive native plant species (and other green waste) by public service providers, 2023).

Pre-treatment actions of the plants used for manufacture of the paper pulp and later for production of packaging is very important, as we mention before. In the production only stems are used because they are rich in lignocellulose. The use of waste from invasive plant species to control invasive populations were perform by several studies on a laboratory scale, but most of them exclude a cost-benefit analysis. Most of the studies cannot be transfer in real lifetime management. The use of invasive waste should be adopted within a clear regulatory framework to avoid bias in the utilization of this waste (Lorenzo and Morais, 2023). Because of the lack of real scale examples using plants for recycling purposes, the majority of public area maintainers (70 %) are not willing to separate plants parts and thereby contribute to increasing the share of recycling. To such high percentage also contributes the fact, that pre-treatment preparation of the plants is time-consuming mainly manual work and the lack of staff (Data from survey: Removal, collection and management of invasive native plant species (and other green waste) by public service providers, 2023).

There is a variety of non-native species that distinguish from each other. Some plants, such as Japanese knotweed and spotted knapweed, have resilient rhizomes, extensive root structures, and hardy seeds that can survive and regrow (Department of Environmental Conservation, 2019). The proper handling of the plant parts of IAS varies among the species themselves. Certain species are very well adapted to difficult environmental conditions and have different survival mechanisms (e.g. the seeds of some plants can survive for several years before germinating). A quarter of public area maintainers already separately collect

invasive plants by species. So far, separate collection of invasive species has been shown to be the key in the recycling processes.

The Institute of Nature Protection of the Republic of Slovenia prepared the document TREATMENT OF RESIDUES OF INVASIVE NON-NATIVE PLANTS: Expert opinion based on a study of the literature, which is helpful with the questions/ambiguities of handling with different parts of invasive plants.

English name	Scientific name	GREEN PARTS (LEAVES AND STEMS)			FLOWERS, SEEDS, FRUITS AND ROOTS		
		Home composting	Aerobic and anaerobic decomposition	Incineration facilities	Home composting	Aerobic and anaerobic decomposition	Incineration facilities
IAS of Union concern							
Common Milkweed	<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Himalayan balsam	<i>Impatiens glandulifera</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Kudzu	<i>Pueraria lobata</i>	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓
Giant Hogweed	<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Tree of Heaven	<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
Water hyacinth	<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Skunk Cabbage	<i>Lysichiton americanus</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Nuttall's Waterweed	<i>Elodea nuttallii</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Other selected IAS							
Canadian Waterweed	<i>Elodea canadensis</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Canada Goldenrod	<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Giant Goldenrod	<i>Solidago gigantea</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Japanese Knotweed	<i>Fallopia japonica</i>	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Common Ragweed	<i>Ambrosia</i> spp.	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
American Pokeweed	<i>Phytolacca americana</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
Indian pokeweed	<i>Phytolacca acinosa</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
daisy fleabane	<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Hacienda Creeper	<i>Parthenocissus</i> spp.	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Wild Cucumber	<i>Echinocystis lobata</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Staghorn sumac	<i>Rhus typhina</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓
Indigo Bush	<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Black Locust	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Foxglove Tree	<i>Paulownia tomentosa</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓

Figure 3. Guidelines for handling with different parts of invasive plant species. Source: Strgulc Krajšek, 2016.

Generally, the safest way to dispose invasive plant material is by putting plant material in bags and dispose it at a landfill or incineration station, followed by composting in composting plants and anaerobic decomposition in biogas plants. Due to large invasive plant populations and resulting high quantity of green waste in some regions, burying it at a landfill may not be the most environmentally-friendly option. Composting facilities may not reach high enough temperatures to inactivate certain invasive plant material, such as seeds. Knotweeds and hawkweeds are two groups of invasive plants that are able to survive high compost temperatures (Invasive Species Council of BC, 2021). For

this reason, it is extremely important these species are disposed of properly through incineration or disposal in landfill, and don't end up in home composter.

It is even more difficult to obtain data or draw a conclusion about the method of collection and handling of non-native plants in case of the removal on private land. In most cases, private landowners throw IAS into the domestic compost bin or leave the biomass at the removal site. Such handling, especially in the case of invasive plants, is very questionable, as invasive plants are highly adaptable and easily move into to new areas by seed or vegetative fragment dispersal, especially during the flowering period. If private landowners bring green garden waste to the collection center, with the questionnaire we obtained some insight of further removal actions.

30 % of collection centers already collect non-native plants separately if citizens bring them separately from other green waste. A little less than half of the collection centers handover the collected non-native plants to aerobic decomposition to the composting facilities (44 %). Only a smaller share is sent to incineration (8 %). Around a quarter of the collection centers handover the green garden waste to landfill sites, which is not the best option of further handling with IAS, as in the mix of the green garden waste there could be some problematic invasive species (Data from survey: Removal, collection and management of invasive native plant species (and other green waste) by public service providers, 2023).

According to the diverse results of the survey questionnaire, currently in Slovenia is a lack of guidelines and regulations regarding the invasive species control. Based on this, our strategy within the LEAP project is to provide residents, businesses and the local community with collection point to handover problematic plant species, where efficient and correct handling of invasive plants are taken and preparation for secondary purposes, production of paper pulp and later protective packaging for household appliances. At the same time, different educational and awareness materials about invasive species, production and importance of packaging based on alternative cellulose fibers are design, which will be reflected in the development of the teaching-demonstration network. As part of this, consortium is setting up an online info point and a demonstration center with various learning content for different target populations.

In the scope of the LEAP project, Surovina organized a removal invasive plants day in the month of May, in order to educate and raise awareness regarding the invasive plants, problems and proper disposal processes. During that day, correct method of removing invasive plants and pre-treatment procedure, that need to be taken for the use of stems in the manufacturing processes, was demonstrated

to local community. Example of the correct preparation of invasive plant waste for handover to collection center in Maribor was presented. For awareness purposes, Surovina prepared educational material regarding two invasive plant species.

Figure 4. Educational material for awareness purposes.

3 PROPER MANAGEMENT OF INVASIVE NATIVE PLANT SPECIES

Handling with invasive species always open the question, how to disposal plant parts, to avoid spread in the environment. Improper disposal is a major pathway of introduction, as invasive plants are often disposed of in ways that allow their seeds or plant parts to be dispersed. In Slovenia is the lack of information and places, such as collection points, to properly dispose of invasive species. The results of the survey questionnaire show us, that handling with invasive plants is very different among of the economic public service providers. Everything between burning debris on-site, which is not legally and formally sufficiently regulated, to handing it over to incinerator plants, composting facilities, or landfill plants, and leaving waste material at the place of origin. Removal and control of invasive alien species is essential from the point of view of prevention and reducing damage.

There are three main disposal options available for invasive plants: land filling, incineration (in incineration plants, on-site) or biological decomposition (aerobic and anaerobic). Removal of invasive alien plant species is most effective before flowering, as the most common way of spread is by seeds. How we treat a plant depends very much on the part of the plant (Invasive Species Council of BC, 2021).

Table 4. Disposal options for invasive plants. Source: Invasive Species Council of BC, 2021.

Disposal Method	Slovenian Regulation	Pros	Cons
<i>Landfilling</i>	<i>Regulation on waste disposal sites</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By putting plant material in bags minimizes the spread in the environment • Special precautions must be taken to ensure separate burial from other waste and that plastic bags are not torn at landfills that dispose invasive plants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Takes up space in landfill • Contributes to greenhouse gas emissions • Increases plastic in landfills • Good option for disposing of small volumes of invasive plant material (time consuming process)
<i>Burning on-site</i>	<i>Regulation on fire protection in the natural environment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimizes movement of plant material • Limits potential spread of invasive materials during transport • Cost-effective • Easy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Special precautions must be taken to ensure that wind don't spread seed through the air (e.g. goldenrod, large linden) • Home burning don't destroy most resilient parts of plants • Drying
<i>Industrial incineration</i>	<i>Regulation on waste incinerators and waste co-incineration plants</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most efficient and reliable disposal option for invasive plants (for all parts of plant, including seeds, fruits, roots) - effectively destroy all parts of the plants • Does not take up space in a landfill 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not always available • Uses resources (fuel, electricity) to burn • Source of greenhouse gas emissions
<i>Composting – is a controlled, aerobic (oxygen-required) process that converts organic materials into smaller constituent parts, with the help of chemical reactions</i>	<i>Home composting: Regulation on handling biodegradable kitchen waste and green garden waste</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmentally-friendly • Closed composting: all requirement parameters such as humidity, the highest temperature reached, the duration of the highest temperature reached, the minimum number of days with the highest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open composting: Not guaranteed for all invasive plant species that reproductive parts will be rendered non-viable – good option for certain species. • Home composting: special precautions must be taken (regular monitoring

<p><i>of micro- and macro-organisms. Home composting Open composting Closed composting</i></p>	<p><i>Industrial composting: Regulation on the processing of biodegradable waste and the use of compost or digestate</i></p>	<p><i>temperature reached and the number of turns of the compost mass are reached – hygienization (destroy all parts of the plants, including seeds)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Compost</i> 	<p><i>of composter) to ensure/prevent invasive alien plants to resprout.</i></p>
<p><i>Anaerobic decomposition – is a controlled, anaerobic (absence of oxygen) process that converts organic materials into smaller constituent parts, with the help of chemical reactions of micro- and macro-organisms.</i></p>	<p><i>Regulation on the processing of biodegradable waste and the use of compost or digestate</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Suitable for waste with a high moisture content (food waste, sludge from sewage treatment plants, IAS)</i> • <i>No large amounts of additional structural material needed</i> • <i>Biogas - energy source (for heating, electricity, biofuel)</i> • <i>Digestate (fertilizer)</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Smells</i> • <i>Not guaranteed for all invasive plant species that reproductive parts will be rendered non-viable – good option for certain species.</i>

Disposal of invasive plants mostly dependent on the local waste facilities and their contracts with the recycling or incineration companies. The most efficient method to dispose invasive plant material is incineration. With the high temperature in incineration plants all parts of the plants burned. But on the other hand, incineration plants are very energy consuming (fuel, electricity) and source of greenhouse gas emissions.

By using the stems of invasive plants for secondary purposes, we reduce the consumption of primary raw materials for the production of paper pulp products. At the same time, the project contributes to the implementation of Directive (EU) 2019/904 on reducing the impact of certain plastic products on the environment with a sustainable transition to a circular economy based on biodegradability, increasing reuse and recycling, reducing the disposal and incineration of waste packaging and the use of raw materials. Also, by switching from EPS to bio-cellulose packaging, we directly influence the reduction of CO₂ emissions, which is in line with the action plan of the European circular economy, which is an important pillar of the European Green Agreement.

4 CONCLUSION

The strategy of the LEAP project is to establish a suitable system for collecting, preparing and producing protective packaging or other paper pulp-based products, out of invasive alien plants. The first very important step is to develop efficient collecting method for invasive plants. Company Surovina inaugurate a collection point in Maribor, to accept invasive plant wastes and properly prepare stems for production of paper pulp and the product. In this manner, any help from local communities is more than welcome, therefor Surovina organized demonstration-collection day, where new strategy for collecting invasive plants was presented. New strategy was devised with the help of the results of a survey conducted among public service providers. Because it is a new way of collecting and preparing plants for secondary purposes, which demand additional work and is time consuming, the maintainers of public areas are not in favor of such a method of collection.

Based on the current situation in the field of removal and handling of invasive alien plant species, we devised new recommendations and established a teaching-demonstration network with the aim of raising awareness and educating the public.

The removal of invasive species from the environment must always be undertaken thoughtfully and in compliance with the regional/national regulation. Handling with invasive plants requires planned strategy to prevent spreading in the environment. Invasive plant species always removed before or after flowering to avoid involuntary seed dispersal. Removal is most effective in the case of individual plants or small stands, consider how the invasive plant grows (tubers, fragments, and seeds) and removed all reproductive parts. To decrease the bigger populations, regular mowing is necessary. The most important measure, however, is to inform and raise awareness among the public about the impacts of invasive species and the correct removal and handling of plant parts, which the LEAP project is committed to.

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